

Paediatric Endodontics (Part 1)

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Paediatric dentistry deals with the total and comprehensive oral health care of children. It deals with all aspects of oral care from prevention to restorative procedures. Despite of the best efforts of the dental professionals emphasizing on prevention, the threat to the pulp by caries, restorative dental treatment, and traumatic injuries, have not been eliminated. The children continue to lose their teeth prematurely. The procedures in the contemporary dental practices are aimed at preventing and treating pulp disease in the primary and immature permanent dentitions.

It was not too long ago when Pediatric dentistry procedures were primarily extraction oriented though it has evolved in the last few years. Extensive progress has been made for prevention of caries and in treatment to deal with the inflamed and infected pulps.

Many professionals question the need to preserve the pulpally involved primary teeth since it involves so much of effort to do so. These practitioners feel that such efforts may present a risk to developing permanent dentition and in any case the deciduous teeth will be eventually lost soon. One of the primary objectives of paediatric dentistry is to preserve the arch space whenever possible since the premature loss of primary teeth may lead to irregular eruption pattern and the malocclusion associated with it. It also affects the aesthetics and mastication, prevent aberrant tongue habits, helps in speech, and prevent the psychological effects that may be associated with a tooth loss.

The primary objective of the professionals is to maintain within the primary teeth in the dental arch in a functional and disease-free condition as long as possible without disturbing the eruption pattern.

When would a child need endodontic treatment?

As with adults, the pulp of a child's tooth – which contains the tooth's nerve — can become injured or infected, requiring endodontic treatment to try and save the tooth. Endodontic treatment may be required in case the child-

- Experiences pain in a tooth at any time, for no apparent reason.

- Has a tooth that's very sensitive to temperature changes, both hot and cold.
- Has broken or cracked teeth with exposed pulp.
- The children might need endodontic treatment not only in the permanent teeth but also in the deciduous teeth which are extremely important for chewing and speaking, also maintain spaces for the permanent teeth to erupt and replace them. If a child loses a baby tooth prematurely, it can result in neighbouring teeth moving into the empty space, subsequently not allowing the permanent tooth from coming in and leading to crooked teeth.

What kind of endodontic treatments are offered for paediatric patients?

- Children typically have underdeveloped roots and thin canal walls, which may require special care in order to treat and restore teeth to a natural and healthy state. Paediatric patients may need –
- Vital pulp therapy procedures, like apexogenesis and apexification. A restorative treatment to preserve and maintain pulp tissue that has been compromised but not destroyed by tooth decay or traumatic injury to a tooth.
- Pulp regeneration. A biologically-based procedure to replace damaged tooth structures.

Child may have anxiety issues about going to the dentist, treatments can be carried out under sedation.

The various options are-

▲ Nitrous Oxide

More commonly known as “laughing gas,” nitrous oxide is a safe agent that is mixed with oxygen and breathed in and out through a mask that rests on the nose. Nitrous oxide is useful in reducing anxiety and helping patients relax while their treatment is being completed. The child will remain awake and aware during this procedure.

▲ IV Sedation

This method of sedation will also ensure your child receives his or her endodontic care in a safe and stress-free environment. While under IV sedation, he or she

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will be unaware of the length of treatment time, helping to prevent the development of concerns and anxiety surrounding future dental and endodontic care.

★ General Anaesthesia

General Anaesthesia is sometimes necessary for children that are unable, either by age or maturity level, to cooperate during dental treatment. With General Anaesthesia, the child will be given medicine to put him or her into a deep sleep – an unconscious state. A thorough medical examination is carried out before administering the general anaesthesia. The anaesthetic medications are delivered through an IV line, although inhaled anaesthetics may also be used. A breathing tube may be inserted during the procedure to safeguard the child's airway throughout the procedure.

Successful pulpal therapy in the primary dentition requires a thorough understanding of primary pulp morphology, root formation, and the special features associated with physiologic resorption of primary tooth roots.

According to Finn and Nelson and Ash, there are 12 basic differences between primary and permanent teeth;

- Primary teeth are smaller in all dimensions than corresponding permanent teeth.
- Primary crowns are wider in the mesial-to-distal dimension compared with crown length than are permanent crowns.
- Primary teeth have narrower and longer roots compared to crown length and width in permanent teeth.
- The facial and lingual cervical thirds of the crowns of anterior primary teeth are much more prominent than those of permanent teeth.
- Primary teeth are markedly more constricted at the dentino-enamel junction (DEJ) than are permanent teeth.
- The facial and lingual surfaces of primary molars converge occlusally; therefore, the occlusal

surface is much narrower in the facio-lingual dimension than the cervical width.

- The roots of primary molars are comparatively more slender and longer than the roots of permanent molars.
- The roots of primary molars flare out from the cervical area, and more at the apex, than do the roots of permanent molars.
- The enamel is thinner (approximately 1 mm) on primary teeth than on permanent teeth, and has a more consistent depth.
- The thickness of the dentin between the pulp chamber and enamel in primary teeth is less than in permanent teeth.
- The pulp chambers in primary teeth are comparatively larger than those in permanent teeth.
- The pulp horns, especially the mesial horns, are higher in primary molars than in permanent molars.

Root Canal Anatomy

To treat the pulps of primary teeth successfully, the clinician must have a thorough knowledge of the anatomy of the primary root canal systems and the variations that exist within them.

Root canal considerations in primary teeth-

- After root-length completion, dentin deposition continues in the root canal.
- After root-length completion, dentin deposited in a root canal may change the number, size, and shape of the root canals.
- Often root canal variations are not visible on clinical radiographic images.
- In anterior teeth, one root canal is usually present, although mandibular incisors occasionally have two.
- In anterior teeth, accessory and lateral canals and apical ramifications are rare.

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